

quality (long and slender), 1,000-grain weight of 23.5 g, good milling percentage (70.2%), and good head rice recovery (56%). Intermediate amylose content is 22.8%. It has an average yield potential of 6–6.5 t ha⁻¹ with multiple disease and insect pest resistance (highly resistant to false smut; resistant to neck blast; moderately resistant to sheath rot, bacterial leaf blight, rice tungro virus, and stem borer). Sahyadri-2 is suitable for upland and double-cropped areas in the state and was recommended for

commercial cultivation in Maharashtra in 2004.

Sahyadri-3 is a medium-duration (125–130 d), mid-tall (115–120 cm), long slender grain type, with an average grain yield potential of 6.5–7.0 t ha⁻¹. It has given a 5–10% yield increase over Sahyadri in farm trials, state and national coordinated trials, and in farmers' fields. Sahyadri-3 has greater milling percentage (74.5%) and head rice recovery (60.2%) than Sahyadri.

Genetic contribution of ancestors to Nepalese rice cultivars

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Nepal is divided into three agro-ecological zones—tarai, mid-hill, and high hill. Research on rice, Nepal's most important crop, is conducted on the basis of what these zones require and recommendations are made accordingly. The mid- and high hills have more diverse climatic conditions than the tarai. Diverse landraces are being cultivated and maintained in these areas to meet various needs of farmers. However, genetic uniformity has been observed after the release of some cultivars. This became a major concern to plant breeders after the 1970 corn leaf blight incidence. The objective of this study was to determine the relative genetic contribution of ancestral lines of Nepalese rice cultivars recommended for the mid- and high hills of Nepal. Knowing the genetic background of these cultivars would be useful in breeding programs to widen the genetic base and increase yield.

The genetic base of 20 rice cultivars, which were recommended for the mid- and high hills, was studied. The parental contribution of an ancestral genotype to a modern cultivar was determined following the procedure of Delanox et al (1983). Ancestors were defined as founding stocks with no known pedigree. The contribution of an ancestor was defined as the fraction of the genes in modern cultivars that could be traced from the progeny of that ancestor

through pedigree analysis. The genetic contribution corresponds to the theoretical proportion of genes coming from an ancestor, assuming that every time a cross is made, 50% of the genes come from each parent.

A total of 47 ancestors originating in 12 countries were used to develop 20 Nepalese rice cultivars that were recommended for the mid- and high hills (figure). The analysis revealed that the genetic base of these recommended

Countries where ancestors of Nepalese improved rice cultivars recommended for the mid- and high hills originated. (Origins of nine ancestors are not known.)

cultivars was fully defined by 47 ancestors. These ancestors' contribution to the genetic base varied from 0.04% to 11.2% (Table 1). A restricted number of ancestral genotypes accounted for a large proportion of the variation in the released cultivars. The highest contribution was from Dee-geo-woo-gen, which was used in 12 cultivars. Eight ancestors contributed 50%. Most of the cultivars were developed using fewer than four ancestors, indicating a narrow genetic base. With a greater number of parents, fewer alleles are fixed and more genetic variation is retained (St. Martin 1982). This shows that rice breeders have made progress at the expense of losing substantial portions of genetic variation originally available.

Many researchers have reported similar results. Dilday (1990) found a narrow genetic base for the southern rice belt; he traced back to 22 ancestors 140 lines from the U.S. rice breeding programs. Ten introductions contributed collectively to >80% of the northern gene pool of soybean (Delannax et al 1983). In barley, five ancestors contributed more than 50% of the genetic makeup of released cultivars (Martin et al 1991).

Table 1. Ancestors' contribution to the genetic base of Nepalese rice cultivars.

Ancestor	Origin	Contribution (%)	Cumulative contribution (%)	Varieties contributed (no.)	Variety	Ancestors used to develop variety (no.)
Dee-geo-woo-gen	Taiwan	11.2	11.2	12	Chianan 2	3
Ghandruk Local	Nepal	7.5	18.7	2	Chianung 242	4
Pokhreli Masino	Nepal	7.5	26.2	3	Chandhanath 1	1
Fuji-102	Japan	5.0	31.2	2	Chandhanath 3	1
Jinling-78-102	China	5.0	36.2	1	Chhommrong	1
Tsai Yuan Chung	Taiwan	5.0	41.2	2	Himali	5
Yunlen-1	China	5.0	46.2	1	Kancahn	13
Jerak	?	4.4	50.5	4	Khumal 4	13
Cina	China	3.8	54.3	10	Khumal 5	5
Latisail	Pakistan	3.8	58.2	10	Khumal 7	5
Kn-1b-214-1-4-3	Indonesia	3.8	61.9	1	Khumal 11	3
Akiyudaka	Korea	2.5	64.4	1	Khumal 2	5
China 1039	India	2.5	66.9	1	Khumal 3	6
China-1039-DWF-MUT	China	2.5	69.4	1	Khumal 6	17
Jarneli	Nepal	2.5	71.9	1	Khumal 9	2
Kulu	Australia	2.5	74.4	1	Machhapuchhre 3	2
Taichung-65	Taiwan	2.5	76.9	1	Manjushri 2	19
Gp-15	?	1.7	78.6	4	Palung 2	6
China 971	China	1.3	79.9	1	Taichung 176	2
Dunghan Shalil	?	1.3	81.1	1	Tainan 1	2

Table 2. Origin of ancestors and their contribution to Nepalese rice cultivars.

Country	Cumulative contribution (%)	Number contributed		Group/species	Cumulative contribution (%)	Number contributed	
		Cultivars	Ancestors			Cultivars	Ancestors
Taiwan	24.8	14	9	Indica	48.2	13	23
Nepal	18.1	7	4	Japonica	33.1	9	11
China	17.6	14	5	Unknown	18.7	13	13
India	6.4	6	9				
Japan	6.3	3	2				
Indonesia	5.3	5	3	<i>sativa</i>	99.8	16	46
Pakistan	3.8	10	1	<i>nivara</i>	0.2	4	1
Australia	2.5	1	1				
Korea	2.5	1	1				
USA	0.4	4	1				
Vietnam	0.2	2	1				
Philippines	0.0	1	1				
Unknown	12.2	10	9				

The origin of most of the ancestors of these Nepalese cultivars was Taiwan (19.1%), India (19.1%), China (10.6%), Nepal (8.5%), Indonesia (6.4%), and Japan (4.3%). On the basis of contribution, ancestors from Taiwan (24.8%), Nepal (18.1%), China (17.6%), India (6.4%), Japan (6.3%), and Indonesia (5.3%) constituted 78.4% of the total contribution (Table 2). Most of the predominant introductions came from the same geographical areas. Ancestors from China

and Taiwan each contributed to 14 cultivars, followed by those of Pakistani origin. About 50% of the ancestors were of the indica type, which contributed 48.2%. Only two species, *sativa* and *nivara*, were used. The mid- and high hills are relatively cool regions where japonica-type landraces are being cultivated. However, the contribution of indica-type ancestors was high in these released cultivars. The diversity present at the species and varietal levels should be considered in

planning breeding programs to control genetic erosion and vulnerability, which is a great possibility because of the observed genetic uniformity. Reshuffling the genetic constituents is also necessary to increase yield potential.

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IRH1—the first aromatic hybrid rice in Iran

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Increasing rice production in Iran, a country with limited land and water resources, is a challenging task, especially with consumer demand largely favoring varieties with superior grain quality. In 2000, Iran imported 1.2 million t of rice. But, in recent years, with increased adoption of improved varieties and with favorable climatic conditions, importation has been reduced to 0.98 million t (FAO 2006). However, with recent fluctuations in the availability of surplus rice from rice-exporting countries and the increasing rice demand in Asia alone, Iran has to initiate a well-drawn plan to attain self-sufficiency and sustain its rice production in the long term. Among the available approaches, the most viable is to pursue hybrid rice technology for Iran, on the basis of success achieved in India, Vietnam, and the Philippines. Hybrid rice technology could easily deliver hybrids with medium quality in the short term, with a 1.5–2.0 t ha⁻¹ advantage over improved check varieties (such as Khazar), while superior quality with high yield can be combined in the hybrids,

provided a systematic approach is followed.

A comparative yield trial in 2002 involving four promising hybrids and their parents and inbred check variety Khazar revealed exceptional performance of the hybrid combination IR58025A/IR42686R. This hybrid gave the highest standard heterosis (57.9%), heterobeltiosis (53.3%), and commercial heterosis (45.2%) over improved check variety Khazar (Table 1). Furthermore, the number of days to 50% flowering of the parents differed by only 3, with the R line flowering earlier and having a relatively

better quality than Khazar (data not shown).

A pooled analysis of variance for the adaptive yield trial conducted over two different sites for 2003-04 showed significant yield differences among genotypes and in site-by-genotype-by-year interaction. IR58025A/IR42686R gave an average yield of 9.2 t ha⁻¹ with a yield advantage of 28% over Khazar (Table 1). It was named IRH1.

On-farm trials conducted in 2005 at four locations gave an impressive yield of 12 t ha⁻¹, which was 85% higher than Khazar's 6.5 t ha⁻¹ (Table 2). The hybrids

Table 1. Yields (kg ha⁻¹) of IRH1 (IR58025A/IR42686R) and check varieties in advanced yield and adaptive trials and associated heterosis (%) based on means across sites.^a

Genotype	Rasht*	Chaparsar*	Mean*	Standard heterosis	Heterobeltiosis	Commercial heterosis
<i>Advanced yield trial, 2002</i>						
IR58025A /IR42686R	8,964 A	9,425 A	9,195 A	57.9	53.3	45.2
IR42686R	5,480 J	5,822 I	5,651 J	–	–	–
IR58025B	5,872 H	6,125 G	5,998 G	–	–	–
Khazar (inbred check)	6,445 F	6,220 F	6,332 F	–	–	–
<i>Adaptive research trial, 2003-04</i>						
IR58025A /IR42686R	8,964	9,425	9,195	–	–	28.0
IR42686R	5,651	5,425	5,568	–	–	–
Khazar (inbred check)	6,942	7,422	7,182	–	–	–

^aIn the advanced yield trial, means followed by different letters in a column are significantly different from each other using DMRT.